

Ukraine-China Bilateral Trade (2008-2018): Threats and Opportunities

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Abstract

China is the world's leading manufacturer and at the same time the largest fast-growing market with sustainable demand for all types of commodities. For Ukraine, China is a major trade partner in Asia, second global trade partner after the Russian Federation and its possible substitute as a destination of Ukrainian export. However, growing turnover of Ukraine-China bilateral trade may also pose a threat to Ukrainian external economic security. This article aims to analyze the contemporary bilateral trade between Ukraine and China to identify possible threats, provide recommendations to minimize the negative impact of trade on the Ukrainian economy. To meet these objectives methods of evaluation of competitiveness and probability of competition with a certain partner in commodities trade are considered. Using tech-intensity decomposition and Revealed Comparative Advantage Index quality and effectiveness of Ukraine-China bilateral trade was evaluated and revealed. It was determined that during the researched time interval bilateral trade between Ukraine and China deteriorated in terms of quality and export composition and now poses a significant threat to Ukrainian economic security. Possible actions to prevent and avoid severe competition and improve trade relations were proposed.

Keywords: Bilateral Trade, Economic Security, Revealed Comparative Advantage, China, Ukraine

Introduction

For the past decade since its entrance to World Trade Organization (WTO) in May of 2008 Ukraine was struggling to modernize its economy to better fit the standards of the European Union. The negotiations to sign the Association Agreement with the EU demanded the cancellation of all previous clandestine or non-ratified agreements between Ukraine, the Russian Federation, and its associates in the Eurasian Economic Union. The geopolitical conflict with Russia that began in 2014 ensured the dismantlement of the traditional trade routes and proved to be a severe blow to Ukrainian machinery and metallurgy that were strongly dependent on the Russian market. To rebalance external trade and find a suitable substitute for Russia as its main trade partner, Ukraine needs to consider every possible partner in Europe, Asia, and the Americas. The People's Republic of China is already among the major partners of Ukraine and has a seemingly unlimited demand for a wide range of commodities including the articles of traditional Ukrainian exports (electrical machinery, mechanical appliances, ores, oilseeds, etc.). However, the dynamics of Ukraine-China bilateral trade relations for the past decade have not been exclusively positive. The objective of this article is to provide extensive quantitative and qualitative analysis of Ukrainian-Chinese bilateral trade, evaluate its efficiency, identify existing and possible threats to Ukrainian external economic security, and to provide recommendations and guidelines to correct the negative aspects and maximize the positive potential.

Ukraine-China bilateral trade relations and their impact on trade security are actively discussed both in the Ukrainian and the international scientific community (Levkivsky, 2013; Antoniuk & Khomenko, 2017; Loiko & Ramskyi, 2018; Raišienė et al., 2019). However, the rapid changes both in the national economy of Ukraine and the global environment demand constant updates of all data and analytics concerning trade and external economic security, especially where major partners are involved. To understand the threats for external economic security and possibilities of expanding trade with China a complex analysis must be conducted by using statistical panel data enhanced by applying analytical indices and coefficients. A set of such indicators was introduced both by Ukrainian scholars (Babets, 2011) and official Ukrainian institutions. According to the Decree of the Ministry of Economic Development and Trade of Ukraine, the external economic security of the country includes several macroeconomic trade indicators and parameters (Ministry of Economic Development..., 2019). The disadvantage of this approved methodology is the use of purely quantitative characteristics, without taking into account the qualitative parameters of international trade. In this study in order to evaluate the level of external trade security a methodology proposed by the Ministry was modified by supplementing and emphasizing the use of the following indicators: (1) export coverage ratio; the share of the partner country in foreign trade; (2) the share of high-tech products in the total export (import); (3) the share of raw materials in the total export; (4) comparative advantages or disadvantages of export portfolio.

Theoretical Framework

To determine the volume and share of trade in high-tech goods in the overall commodity trade turnover it is necessary to decompose the general trade profile to highlight the technological component of different commodity groups. For this purpose, the classification of industries by their level of technological intensity according to the OECD method is used. To maintain consistency of the chosen methodology, all statistical data is provided by the International Trade Center (ITC) and converted from the Harmonized System (HS) to the International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC) according to the following correspondence table.

Table 1: Manufacturing industries ranked by OECD according to their global technological intensity (ISIC Revision 2; HS, 2-digits)

Level of technological intensity	Branches of industry	Code of commodity group	
		HS, 2-digits	ISIC Rev. 2.
High technology (R&D expenditure is more than 5%)	Aerospace; computers, office machinery; electronics-communications; pharmaceuticals	30; 80; 90; 93	3522; 3825; 3832; 3845
Medium-high-technology (R&D expenditure is 3.0-4.9%)	Scientific instruments; motor vehicles; electrical machinery; chemicals; other transport equipment; non-electrical machinery.	28-29; 32; 84-87	385; 3843; 383-3832; 351+352+3522; 3842+3844+3849; 382-3825
Medium-low-technology (R&D expenditure is 1.0-2.9%)	Rubber and plastic products; shipbuilding; other manufacturing; non-ferrous metals; non-metallic mineral products; fabricated metal products; petroleum refining; ferrous metals.	25-27; 31; 33-36; 38-40; 68-83; 89; 91-92	355+356; 3841; 39; 372; 36; 381; 351+354; 371
Low-technology (R&D expenditure is less than 0.9%)	Paper printing; textile and clothing; food, beverages, and tobacco; wood and furniture	01-24; 37; 41-67; 94-97	34; 32; 31; 33

Source: Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD); International Trade Center (ITC)

The growing presence of Chinese manufacturers on the global market will inevitably increase competition especially in the low-priced industries which historically are Chinese traditional articles of exports. To determine whether China poses a threat to Ukraine as a competitor it is necessary to compare the export portfolio of both countries and determine whether Ukrainian goods have a comparative advantage over Chinese goods in the global market.

Revealed Comparative Advantage Index (RCA) was first introduced in 1965 to indirectly measure comparative advantage from the perspective of commodity exports, and it is currently widely used by international organizations such as the World Bank and United Nations (Balassa, 1965; Mikic & Gilbert, 2007). RCA is based on the Ricardian comparative advantage concept and uses the trade pattern to identify the sectors in which an economy has an advantage, by comparing the country of interests' trade profile with the world average. It is calculated by using the following formula:

$$RCA = \frac{\sum_d x_{isd} / \sum_d X_{sd}}{\sum_{wd} x_{iwd} / \sum_{wd} X_{wd}}, \quad (1)$$

Where s is the country of interest, d and w are the set of all countries in the world, i is the sector of interest, x is the commodity export flow and X is the total export flow. Index can take a range of values between 0 and $+\infty$.

Level of comparative advantage is considered to be very high if the RCA index exceeds 2.5; high if it takes values between 1.25 and 2.5; mediocre\unstable if it takes values between 0.8 and 1.25 and low if the RCA index is less than 0.8 (Cui & Chen, 2016). The RCA index is also affected by any interference that will distort the natural trade pattern (trade barriers, tariff and non-tariff regulation, sanctions, and embargos).

Analysis of Results

According to the State Statistics Service of Ukraine in 2004-2018, the share of China in the total geographical structure of Ukrainian external trade averaged 5.73% (3.32% of total export and 8.15% of total import), effectively making China Ukraine's major trade partner in Asia. The total trade turnover (excluding services) increased from 1.56 to 9.81 bln USD (average annual growth rate of turnover was 17.9%). Export increased from 0.82 to 2.21 bln USD (14.76%), and import increased from 0.74 to 7.6 bln USD (27.32%). Until 2013, there was a clear tendency for a constant increase in the total volume of trade; after 2013 there was been a two-year decline in overall trade due to economic and political turmoil in Ukraine. After 2015, the volume of trade is growing again with the same tendency as observed before the crisis.

The dynamics of the basic indicators of bilateral trade between Ukraine with China indicate the unstable nature of trade conditions and the prevalence of import over export. Since 2005, the export-to-import ratio has been lower than one unit (0.29 in 2018) and the foreign trade balance was negative (in 2018 negative balance amounted to -5.39 bln USD), and did not meet threshold values of external economic security. The negative trade balance has a disruptive impact on national economic security, exacerbates the pressure on the national currency's exchange rate and creates a deficit of foreign currency.

Equally dangerous for the development of Ukraine's economy is the filling of its national market with Chinese processed consumer goods with high technological intensity. The conducted decomposition of trade by level of technological intensity (figure 1-2) shows that for the past decade the share of high-tech products in Ukrainian total exports to China was insignificant (mean value of 0.53% of total exports to China or 9.77 mln USD in 2008-2018, almost reaching 1% in 2016 with the record value of 17.53 mln of USD). At the same time the share of medium-low-technology commodities dropped significantly after 2014 and at the end of 2018 amounted only 712.3 mln USD (10% of total export to China) while the amount of low-technology commodities increased

significantly (1267.2 mln of USD; 57.4% of total export to China) marking the transformation of Ukraine from an exporter of processed goods to a source of raw materials to fuel the growing Chinese industry. On the other hand, the import of commodities from China demonstrates a reverse trend with the constant increase in high and medium-high-technology products (2.5% and 55.3% of total import to Ukraine respectively).

Table 2: Dynamics of the basic indicators of bilateral trade in commodities between Ukraine and China, 2004-2018

Year	Export, bln of USD	Import, bln of USD	Trade turnover, bln of USD	Balance, bln of USD	Normalized trade balance.	Export/Import coverage.
2004	0.82	0.74	1.56	0.08	0.05	1.11
2005	0.71	1.81	2.52	-1.1	-0.44	0.39
2006	0.54	2.31	2.85	-1.77	-0.62	0.24
2007	0.43	3.31	3.74	-2.88	-0.77	0.13
2008	0.55	5.6	6.15	-5.05	-0.82	0.1
2009	1.43	2.73	4.17	-1.3	-0.31	0.52
2010	1.32	4.7	6.02	-3.38	-0.56	0.28
2011	2.18	6.27	8.45	-4.09	-0.48	0.35
2012	1.78	7.9	9.68	-6.12	-0.63	0.22
2013	2.73	7.903	10.63	-5.18	-0.49	0.35
2014	2.67	5.41	8.08	-2.73	-0.34	0.49
2015	2.4	3.77	6.17	-1.37	-0.22	0.64
2016	1.83	4.69	6.52	-2.86	-0.44	0.39
2017	2.13	5.64	7.72	-3.51	-0.45	0.38
2018	2.21	7.6	9.81	-5.39	-0.55	0.29

Source: International Trade Center (ITC), 2019; Author's calculations.

Figure 1: Commodity exports from Ukraine to China by level of global technological intensity, 2008, 2014, 2018 (mln of USD)

Source: The International Trade Center (ITC), 2019; Author's calculations

Figure 2: Commodity imports to Ukraine from China by level of global technological intensity, 2008, 2014, 2018 (mln of USD)

Source: The International Trade Center (ITC), 2019; Author’s calculations

Table 3: Revealed Comparative Advantage Index (RCA) of major commodity groups according to Ukrainian classification of foreign economic activity goods (UKTZED), 2018

HS2 code	UKTZED chapter	Title of chapter	RCA Ukraine	RCA China
01–05	I	Live animals; products of animal origin	1.31	0.37
06–14	II	Products of vegetable origin	7.91	0.39
15	III	Animal or vegetable fats and oils...	19.64	0.09
16–24	IV	Prepared foods; beverages...	2.01	0.42
25–27	V	Mineral products	0.64	0.14
28–38	VI	Chemicals and related industries	0.43	0.6
39–40	VII	Polymeric materials, plastics...	0.34	0.94
41–43	VIII	Genuine leather, natural fur...	0.57	2.28
44–46	IX	Wood and wood products; charcoal...	3.98	0.84
47–49	X	Pulp of wood or cellulosic materials...	0.83	0.67
50–63	XI	Textiles and textile products	0.41	2.47
64–67	XII	Shoes, hats, rain and sun umbrellas...	0.49	2.73
68–70	XIII	Articles made of stone, cement...	0.86	2.09
71	XIV	Pearls, precious or semi-precious stones...	0.04	0.24
72–83	XV	Non-precious metals and articles thereof	3.62	1.1
84–85	XVI	Machinery, electrical equipment...	0.38	1.68
86–89	XVII	Vehicles, transport devices...	0.13	0.45
90–92	XVIII	Optical instruments and apparatus...	0.09	0.9
93	XIX	Weapons, ammunition...	-	0.09
94–96	XX	Various goods and products	0.78	3.04
97;99	XXI	Works of art, non-specified goods	0.15	0.1

Data on HS93 “Arms and ammunition; parts and accessories thereof” is unavailable for Ukraine

Source: International Trade Center (ITC), 2019; Author’s calculations

The deformed structure of trade, which is characterized by a low share of high-tech products in export and a predominance of high-tech import leads to external technological dependence and deepening structural disparities in the Ukrainian economy. The technological backwardness of industrial enterprises, the low level of tech-intensity is also exacerbated by ineffective state policy and flawed institutional support for international cooperation, the lack of effective tools to support innovative enterprises.

To rank Ukrainian commodities in terms of comparative advantages and calculate an RCA index, it is necessary to address the more detailed classification of goods beyond their level of technological intensity. Ukrainian classification of foreign economic activity goods (UKTZED) is a commodity nomenclature of the Customs Tariff of Ukraine that is based on the Harmonized system and the Combined Nomenclature used by the countries of the European Union. UKTZED is more detailed compared to ISIC and provides additional information that is necessary to determine the possible threats to economic security as it is interpreted by Ukrainian legislation.

Ukraine maintains high comparative advantage in the export of raw material and medium-low-tech intermediate products such as products of vegetable origin (7.91), animal or vegetable fats and oils (19.64); articles of wood (3.98) and metallurgy (3.62). To determine the RCA for the top 10 commodities in Ukrainian exports an in-depth analysis of trade structure was conducted by addressing the detailed statistics on 98 types of commodities provided by the International Trade Center (ITC) and State Statistics Service of Ukraine (table 4; figure 2).

Table 4: 10 primary commodities of Ukraine's world exports, 2018

UKTZED chapter	HS2 code	Name of commodity	Bln USD	% of total export
I	72	Iron and steel	9.94	20.98
II	10	Cereals	7.24	15.28
III	15	Animal or vegetable fats and oils	4.5	9.5
IV	26	Ores, slag and ash	3.04	6.42
V	85	Electrical machinery and equipment...	2.93	6.19
VI	12	Oil seeds and oleaginous fruits	1.95	4.12
VII	84	Machinery, mechanical appliances...	1.73	3.65
VIII	44	Wood and articles of wood	1.49	3.15
IX	23	Residues and waste from the food industries	1.23	2.6
X	73	Articles of iron or steel	1.12	2.36
-	-	Other 78 commodities	12.2	25.75
-	-	Total exports	47.37	100

Source: International Trade Center (ITC), 2019; State Statistics Service of Ukraine, 2019; Author's calculations

In-depth analysis reveals the same trend of Ukraine having a comparative advantage in raw and intermediate products (iron and steel, cereals, fats and oils, wood, etc.). It needs to be noted that high RCA does not guarantee the competitiveness of a commodity both on the national or global market as this index does not include technological prowess nor quality of the product. The high RCA of cereals and crude metallurgy goods produced in Ukraine does not necessary mean that these respective industries will outperform their Chinese counterparts in the global market and mainly illustrates the overreliance of the Ukrainian economy on these two industries since their shares in exports are extraordinarily high (approximately 21% of total exports are crude metals and 15% is cereals).

On the other hand, Chinese exports are more balanced and diversified, with no industry significantly outperforming the others. The advantages are distributed among products of the textile industry and medium-high-tech machinery. This supports the hypothesis about the inter-industrial nature of

Ukraine-China bilateral trade and enhances the outlined threats to Ukraine’s economic security. However, China also has significant disadvantages (both compared to Ukraine and on the global market) in animal and vegetable oils (0.09); mineral products (0.14); military products (0.09) and optical instruments (0.9) which may provide additional possibilities and opportunities for Ukraine to rebalance its trade relations with this partner.

Figure 3: Revealed Comparative Advantage Index (RCA) of 10 primary commodities of Ukraine’s export compared to China’s, 2018

Source: *International Trade Center (ITC), 2019; State Statistics Service of Ukraine, 2019; Author’s calculations*

Discussion & Recommendations

The conducted analysis of trade between Ukraine and China demonstrates a threat of the transformation of Ukraine into a raw material appendage and dependent market not only of the developed countries but also of China. Considering this threat, it is advisable to review the structure of trade as soon as possible, reduce the export of raw materials and low value-added products and introduce measures to increase the export of processed consumption goods.

The biggest downside in bilateral trade with China is the increase in the share of mineral raw materials accompanied by a decrease in the import of the finished and intermediate industrial products of Ukrainian producers, which is especially noticeable in the iron and steel trade (commodity group HS72). In 2001, iron and steel dominated the export portfolio of Ukrainian-Chinese trade (378.26 mln of USD, 78% of total domestic exports to China), in 2018 export of steel to China decreased to 5.3 mln of USD or less than 1% of total export to China. This rapid decrease is primarily attributed to competition from Chinese metal industries: in 2004 China’s steel production reached 272.8 million tons exceeding domestic consumption of 215 million tons. In the following years, the demand for steel in China has gradually decreased with the completion of industrialization (Hu et al., 2008). China is now the world’s largest producer and exporter of steel.

Since 2007, Chinese manufacturers have been expanding their presence in the Middle East region to which Ukraine is currently exporting approximately 35% of her domestic steel. Pressure from Chinese manufacturers will inevitably increase in this region since the Middle East and North Africa are becoming one of the most promising markets for steel. It should be noted that China’s exports of steel have been a subject of frequent anti-dumping or countervailing measures. Given the

membership in WTO Ukraine may address this organization in case of unfair competition caused by the Chinese government-sponsored enterprises (Fojtikova, 2017).

Despite the low level of export of high-tech products, China remains one of Ukraine's major trading partners in the market of military and dual-use goods. It is difficult to evaluate the actual turnover and quality of arms trade with China due to limitations of the RCA index and lack of reliable statistics (data on HS group 93 "Arms and ammunition; parts and accessories thereof" is not published according to Ukrainian legislation). According to the Ukrainian State Company "Ukrspesexport", since 1992 Ukraine and China have signed and successfully executed about 200 contracts in the military and technical field and several major deals were made regarding the transfer of old Soviet military equipment including the infamous "Varyag deal" in 1998 when China acquired its first aircraft carrier presently known as "Liaoning" (Kashin, 2013).

For China, military and dual-use goods from Ukraine are attractive because of their high level of adaptability and quality at a relatively low price compared to competitors. These are primarily aircraft and air-defense systems. However, despite the obvious possibility of increasing the export of high-tech finished goods, it is impossible to ignore the aspirations of China to reduce the backwardness of its national industry and to create its own modern military-industrial complex. The majority of Chinese-produced military equipment historically has been based on the imitation of Soviet and Western models, but this had not prevented China from gaining a significant share of global arms markets mainly by trading with countries that other exporters have ignored because of political reasons. China is particularly interested in the markets of Africa and the Middle East (Zimbabwe, South Sudan, Afghanistan, etc.), where a steady demand for low-cost, easy-to-service military commodities exist (Spiegel & Le Billon, 2009). At the same time, the Middle East is also a priority market for Ukraine. According to data provided by Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (SIPRI, 2019), Pakistan, the largest importer of Ukrainian weapons (1,371 million USD in 1992-2008), has already contracted with China to supply and license the production of Chinese fighter jets. This makes Ukraine and the China rivals in the global arms market and the competition between them is deepening.

To prevent direct competition with China in Ukraine, it is advisable to concentrate military-industrial cooperation on projects and technologies to which Chinese enterprises do not yet have access. An existing strategic cooperation program has already implemented a large-scale project to supply China with the world's largest amphibious assault hovercraft Zubr LCAC. This and other agreements with China have allowed Ukraine to take fourth place in the world in terms of the arms trade, which in 2012 reached \$ 1.334 bln USD (SIPRI, 2019).

However, the transfer of complex military equipment and joint projects with China may lead to a leak of technologies. China is struggling to obtain any Ukrainian industry that produces aircraft engines and equipment, mainly to gain access to the technological process and replicate it. China has already expressed interest in acquiring Ukrainian Antonov An-225s – the world's largest cargo plane. In 2016 Chinese representatives supposedly signed a contract with Antonov to deliver plane parts to state-owned factories in China for further assembly. Only one year later Chinese started to assemble its copies of An-225s. Another similar highly controversial deal of Chinese investment in Ukrainian industry is the acquisition of the "Motor Sich" aircraft engine factory (Troianovski, 2019).

Far safer and more lucrative for Ukrainian producers is the food market of China. For China, with its constantly growing population, food problems and food security remain unsolved problems. Presently, China maintains its food security at the expense of the environment and sustainable development and by controlling the growth and migration of its population, but despite all government efforts, malnutrition continues to be a problem (Huang & Yang). China's food self-sufficiency is likely to fall to 91% in 2025. China seeks to ensure food security through land acquisition and cooperation in the agro-industrial sector. Projections for the same period suggest that over 15% of world trade in maize, soybean, oilseeds, mutton, and dairy will be imported to China (Huang et al., 2017). The expansion of trade in food and agricultural commodities creates opportunities for Ukraine to maximize its natural resource potential in the conditions of development

of the agro-industrial sector, which does not exclude the negative consequences of cooperation since China can't replicate the natural advantage provided by Ukrainian soil and climate.

Conclusion

Analysis of trade patterns demonstrates the existence of certain tendencies that may prove to be a threat to Ukrainian economic security, namely: (1) negative balance of trade with China and the prevailing growth rate of Chinese imports; (2) negative changes in the commodity structure of bilateral trade, a trade deficit with China, excessively high share of high-tech products in imports; (3) the possibility of competition with China in traditional Ukrainian markets (Middle East and North Africa); (4) a loss of comparative advantage because of technology leakage.

To minimize these revealed threats for Ukraine, the priority should be given to overcoming the existing negative aspects of cooperation, avoiding fierce competition and developing mutually beneficial cooperation strategies and programs, especially in the agricultural and aerospace industries. Given the membership of Ukraine and China in the WTO, it is necessary to achieve informational and technological exchange; and to initiate negotiations to avoid unnecessary trade protectionism that may lead to trade war.

The majority of the threats to Ukraine's economic security in trade with China exist primarily due to the uncompetitive structure of the Ukrainian export portfolio which consists of a narrow range of mostly low-tech intermediate goods and raw materials. The Chinese market is aiming to become a self-sustained environment and to reduce its imports from other countries to raw materials that are vital for fueling the growing Chinese manufacturing industries. To avoid becoming the mere supplier of raw materials Ukraine must rebalance its trade with China and focus on exporting the processed food products that are the only type of commodity Chinese won't be able to provide by growing their manufacturing capabilities or reverse-replicating the previously imported technologies.

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